

SONNING PIFAGOR JUFTLIKLARI SONINI TOPISH

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Annotatsiya. Quyida $(a, b; c)$ Pifagor juftligi bo'lsa, u holda a soni b sonining Pifagor jufti bo'lishi haqida, Pifagor uchliklari $(a, b_1; c_1), (a, b_2; c_2), \dots, (a, b_n; c_n)$ berilganda u holda a soni uchun b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n Pifagor juftlari haqida ma'lumot berilgan. Shuningdek a soni b sonining Pifagor jufti bo'lsa, u holda b soni ham a sonining Pifagor jufti ekanligi keltirilgan.

Pifagor sonlari, biror Pifagor soning Pifagor juftlari sonini aniqlash yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Pifagor soni, Pifagor juftlari, Eylar uchligi, Eylar g'ishti, diagonal, to'g'ri burchakli uchburchak, teng yonli uchburchak.

Ma'lumki, istalgan $n, m \in \mathbb{N}$, $n > m$ sonlari yordamida hosil qilingan

$$a = n^2 - m^2, \quad b = 2nm, \quad c = n^2 + m^2 \quad (1)$$

$(a, b; c)$ uchlik Pifagor uchligini bo'ladi. (1) formula yordamida istalgan Pifagor uchligini hosil qilish mumkin [1]- [5].

Endi bir Pifagor uchligi berilgan bo'lsa, uning yordamida yangi Pifagor uchligini hosil qilish usulini bayon qilamiz.

2.5- ta'rif. Agar $(a, b; c)$ Pifagor juftligi bo'lsa, u holda a soni b sonining Pifagor jufti deyiladi.

Bizga Pifagor uchliklari $(a, b_1; c_1), (a, b_2; c_2), \dots, (a, b_n; c_n)$ berilsin, u holda a soni uchun b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n sonlari Pifagor juftlari deb ataladi.

Ta'rifdan kelib chiqadiki, agar a soni b sonining Pifagor jufti bo'lsa, u holda b soni ham a sonining Pifagor jufti bo'ladi.

2.1-teorema. $n = 2k, \forall k \in \mathbb{N}$ juft sonlar Pifagor juftlari (PJS) soni

$$(PJS) (2k) = \frac{NBS(k^2) - 1}{2}$$

2.2-teorema. Ixtiyoriy $n = 2k + 1, \forall k \in \mathbb{N}$ toq sonning Pifagor juftlari soni

$$PJS(2k + 1) = \frac{NBS((2k+1)^2) - 1}{2}$$

$$(2n)^2 + \left(\frac{n^2}{p_i} - p_i\right)^2 = \left(\frac{n^2}{p_i} + p_i\right)^2$$

$\forall n, p_i \in Z$ uchun bunday Pifagor juftlarining soni $((p_i - n^2$ ning turli bo'luvchilari) $\frac{n^2}{p_i} - p_i - p_i < x$ tengsizligini qanoatlantiruvchi butun sonlar soni. Agar biz ayniyatning ikkala qismini p_i ning kvadratiga ko'paytirsak, u holda biz barcha Pifagor sonlarini beradigan klassik formulani olamiz, ya'ni ular orasida $2n$ juft sonli barcha Pifagor juftlari bor, ya'ni

$$(2n)^2 + \left(\frac{n^2}{p_i} - p_i\right)^2 = \left(\frac{n^2}{p_i} + p_i\right)^2$$

$$4n^2 + \frac{n^4}{p_i^2} - 2n^2 + p_i^2 = \frac{n^4}{p_i^2} + 2n^2 + p_i^2$$

tenglik bajariladi va $2n$ juft soni Pifagor juftlarining soni $\frac{n^2}{p_i} - p_i$ sonining butun son yekanligiga bog'liqligidan, u holda $n = 2k, \forall k \in N$ juft soni Pifagor juftlari

$$(PJS) (2k) = \frac{NBS(k^2) - 1}{2}$$

2.1-misol. 72 sonining Pifagor juftlarini topamiz.

Yechish. 1-usul. $k=36$ bo'lgani uchun

$$(2.36)^2 + \left(\frac{36^2}{p_i} - p_i\right)^2 = \left(\frac{36^2}{p_i} + p_i\right)^2$$

$$(2.36)^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{p_i} - p_i\right)^2 = \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{p_i} + p_i\right)^2$$

$\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{p_i}$ kasr butun songa teng bo'lgan shunday $p_i < 36$ ni topamiz.

$$p_1 = 1, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{1} - 1\right)^2 = \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{1} + 1\right)^2 \quad 72^2 + 1295^2 = 1297^2$$

$$p_2 = 2, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{2} - 2\right)^2 = \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{2} + 2\right)^2 \quad 72^2 + 646^2 = 650^2$$

$$p_3 = 3, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{3} - 3\right)^2 = \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{3} + 3\right)^2 \quad 72^2 + 429^2 = 435^2$$

$$p_4 = 4, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{4} - 4\right)^2 = \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{4} + 4\right)^2 \quad 72^2 + 320^2 = 328^2$$

$$p_5 = 6, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{6} - 6\right)^2 = \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{6} + 6\right)^2 \quad 72^2 + 210^2 = 222^2$$

$$p_6 = 8, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{8} - 8\right)^2 = \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{8} + 8\right)^2 \quad 72^2 + 154^2 = 170^2$$

$$p_7 = 9, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{9} - 9\right)^2 = \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{9} + 9\right)^2 \quad 72^2 + 135^2 = 153^2$$

$$p_8 = 12, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{12} - 12\right)^2 = \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{12} + 12\right)^2 \quad 72^2 + 96^2 = 120^2$$

$$p_9 = 16, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{16} - 16\right)^2 = \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{16} + 16\right)^2 \quad 72^2 + 65^2 = 97^2$$

$$p_{10} = 18, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{18} - 18\right)^2 = \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{18} + 18\right)^2 \quad 72^2 + 54^2 = 90^2$$

$$p_{11} = 24, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{18} - 18\right)^2 = \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{18} + 18\right)^2 \quad 72^2 + 54^2 = 90^2$$

$$p_{12} = 27, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{27} - 27\right)^2 = \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{27} + 27\right)^2 \quad 72^2 + 21^2 = 75^2$$

Bundan kelib chiqadiki, biz 72 sonining barcha natural bo'luvchilari sonini topdik.
Demak, $(PJS)(72)=12$.

2-usul. 1-teorema asosida buni ham topish mumkin

$$PJS(72) = \frac{NBS(36^2) - 1}{2} = 12$$

2-misol. 15 sonining Pifagor juftlarini topamiz.

Yechish. 1-usul.

$$p_1 = 1, \quad 15^2 + \left(\frac{\frac{3^2 \cdot 5^2}{2} - 1}{2}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{\frac{3^2 \cdot 5^2}{2} + 1}{2}\right)^2 \quad 15^2 + 112^2 = 113^2$$

$$p_2 = 3, \quad 15^2 + \left(\frac{\frac{3^2 \cdot 5^2}{2} - 3}{2}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{\frac{3^2 \cdot 5^2}{2} + 3}{2}\right)^2 \quad 15^2 + 35^2 = 38^2$$

$$p_3 = 5, \quad 15^2 + \left(\frac{\frac{3^2 \cdot 5^2}{2} - 5}{2}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{\frac{3^2 \cdot 5^2}{2} + 5}{2}\right)^2 \quad 15^2 + 20^2 = 25^2$$

$$p_3 = 9, \quad 15^2 + \left(\frac{\frac{3^2 \cdot 5^2}{2} - 9}{2}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{\frac{3^2 \cdot 5^2}{2} + 9}{2}\right)^2 \quad 15^2 + 8^2 = 17^2$$

2-usul. 2-teoremadan foydalanib, topamiz

$$PJS(15) = \frac{NBS((2k+1)^2) - 1}{2} = 4$$

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